

DYNAMIC GOVERNANCE BASED EDUCATIONAL TOURISM DEVELOPMENT MODEL IN INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

Educational tourism has dynamic developments, as well as problems that change along with global developments, including in Indonesia. It is important to develop educational tourism as an effort to provide learning to the public, and especially school students. The aim of this research is to identify the development of educational tourism in Indonesia, as well as to formulate a policy implementation model in Indonesia. This research uses qualitative methods with discourse network analysis. Data sources were obtained from cyberspace in the form of mass media and trusted articles. Based on the results of the analysis, the results showed that there were 5 actors that could be photographed, namely non-governmental organizations, academics, government, public and private sectors. The five actors expressed several opinions regarding the 9 key issues in this research, namely nature education, innovation, education tourism development, infrastructure, human resources, facilities, technology, history and stakeholders. From the results of these variables, a policy recommendation model was formed which was moderated by the concept of dynamic governance, namely thinking ahead, thinking again, and thinking across.

KEYWORDS

Educational tourism, discourse network analysis, dynamic governance, Indonesia

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is one of the sectors that contributes the largest foreign exchange in Indonesia, in fact in 2019 based on data quoted from jasabisnis.com, tourism was ranked first as the highest contributor of foreign exchange, beating the gas and coal industry, palm oil and clothing industries. Tourism always has dynamic problems that change according to global developments. The policies that are formulated will also adapt to the problems that arise, so they can be viewed from the concept of dynamic governance. According to Neo & Chen (2007), the concept of dynamic governance is the government's ability to continuously adjust public policies and programs, as well as patterns of changing the way public policies are formulated and implemented, so that they have an impact on long-term development interests.

Neo and Chen (2007) formulate dynamic governance as "to how these chosen paths, policies, institutions, and structures adapt to an uncertain and fast changing environment so that they remain relevant and effective in achieving the long-term desired outcomes of society . Change is the basic essence in dynamic governance because to be able to adapt the way the government takes in running government to the dynamics of environmental change requires various changes both in terms of planning and implementation. Plans and implementation must be adaptive to the magnitude of uncertainty in the future of the global environment. Change is generally the result of a combination of two elements, namely; organizational culture and organizational capabilities . Neo and Chen (2007) say that capability Dynamic governance consists of three elements, namely thinking ahead, thinking again, and thinking across.

One type of tourism is in the educational sector. Rodger (1998) defines educational tourism as a program in which activity participants travel and tour in a certain place in groups with the main aim of gaining direct learning experience about the location visited. Educational tourism is a vacation and learning activity, with the concept of non-formal educational learning that is not studied in formal schools or courses. Education-based tourism is a type of tourism that combines elements of tourism activities with educational content inside. This tour has various themes with various game rides which can also be used as learning media. This educational tour is very suitable to visit with children because it has many benefits, such as strengthening curiosity, increasing insight, direct learning practice, and various other positive benefits.

Educational tourism is a program that combines elements of tourism activities with educational content inside. This program can be packaged in such a way that annual tourism activities or extracurricular activities have quality and weight. The materials in the guidance have been adjusted to the student's weight and the educational curriculum. Every time you visit a tourist attraction it will be adjusted to the interest of the object and the field of science to be studied.

The e-education tourism program is also supported by higher education academics in delivering material in the field. So this program is really designed to provide quality school tourism activities. It is time for educational tourism programs to be developed in every school as a learning process for students about love of nation, country and homeland. Through promotions, the Indonesian love education tourism program which is specifically for school students, for example, can be a solution to improve community welfare because it is predicted that this activity will be able to move residents around tourist attractions towards a better life. By encouraging the flow of school students to take part in educational tourism programs and requiring students to take part in comparative study programs to various regions, this will certainly provide a breath of fresh air for national tourism development. As a pioneer provider of educational tourism activities in Indonesia, educational tourism can be summed up as a trip to a place to gain learning experiences that build character, thoughts or abilities related to tourist objects and tourist activities carried out with the aim of increasing intelligence and creativity. Educational tourism can be done at various types of tourist attractions, such as museums, botanical gardens, zoos and historical sites. Educational tourism can provide great benefits for visitors, such as increasing knowledge, skills and experience.

Education-based tourism development is a form of innovation in tourist destination development and is related to learning in the concept of learning and playing. Another aim of tourism development is not only to emphasize the development of economic space, settlements and transportation space, but also to pay attention to the community's needs for the provision of appropriate and adequate public space. Public space is an important area in a region as a forum for the public to carry out various activities both individually and together. The development of education-based tourism is currently continuing to grow in various regions in Indonesia. According to Rodger (1998) there are several types of education-based tourism, namely science, sports, culture, agribusiness, history, environmental, social, technological, arts and maritime tourism.

However, according to Nugroho (2020) the development of education-based tourism in Indonesia has various problems, namely:

1. Lack of support from the government in developing educational tourism, such as a lack of budget and policies that support the development of educational tourism
2. The lack of quality human resources in the tourism sector, including educational tourism, makes it difficult to provide good service to tourists

3. There is a lack of publication and promotion regarding educational tourism in Indonesia, so it is less well known by the wider community and less popular with tourists
4. Lack of adequate facilities and infrastructure to support the development of educational tourism, such as lack of adequate transportation and accommodation
5. There is a lack of attention to the development of educational tourism in certain areas, so that the potential for educational tourism in these areas is not utilized optimally

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach with the Discourse Network Analysis (DNA) method. The content can be articles or news released online. The data was then analyzed using the Discourse Network Analyzer. The DNA analysis technique was discovered by Leifeld & Haunss. DNA is a technique that can be used to study certain actors or figures regarding a policy based on validated sources. It is stated that the source used in this research is digital newspapers. DNA is a methodological approach that combines discourse analysis and social network analysis to identify discourse in various documents to create networks. It is stated that DNA combines qualitative-based content analysis, namely discourse analysis with social network analysis, to understand actors' ideas relationally and systematically. This approach makes it possible to systematically identify discourse structures in various textual documents such as newspaper or print media articles or transcripts of debates in parliament (Leifeld & Haunss, 2011).

DNA analysis tends to be used for research studies regarding government policies and conflicts related to a country. One of the studies that previously developed political science using this method was conducted by Philip Leifeld regarding Reconceptualization of Major Policy Changes in Advocacy Coalitions. Leifeld tries to identify the internal weaknesses of major policy reconceptualizations using a case study of German pension politics. DNA analysis is a combination of qualitative content analysis with social network analysis which can provide a measurement of the level of policy trust in the subsystem when the advocacy coalition process takes place (Leifeld & Haunss, 2011). DNA analysis tends to be used to dig up information related to government or state policies. The description above provides space and opportunity for the author to utilize and deepen the discourse on the use of network analysis on other topics related to government policy, namely education-based tourism sentiment.

For this reason, the author wants to use DNA analysis to study phenomena in the implementation of food policy. Some of the advantages of DNA are to obtain the following information.

1. Actors associated with discourse
2. The relationship between actors and concepts in a discourse
3. The relationship between one actor and other actors in a discourse
4. The relationship of a concept with other concepts in a discourse
5. Conceptual sentiment in discourse

The first step of DNA analysis is determining keywords related to the data for the DNA-based data collection stage. The keywords used are "EDUCATIONAL TOURISM", "PROBLEMS", and "DEVELOPMENT". After selecting relevant keywords, the next step is to search for data in the form of news on electronic media pages. The next step is to process the data in the Discourse Network Analyzer application. Then the graphic image is visualized using the

Visone application. After producing images from DNA analysis, descriptive research was carried out regarding the results of the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1. Discourse Network Analysis Output

Based on news searches obtained on the internet and based on mass media or articles, approximately 40 related news items were found. Furthermore, the news is sorted by researchers focused on the topic of this research. Then 10 articles were produced that focused on discussing education-based tourism. After processing it in the Discourse Network Analyzer application and the output is displayed via the Visone application, the output results are obtained as in Figure 1. In this image the sentiment is displayed which is marked with a square icon, then the round icon is the actor who expressed the sentiment. The sentiment expressed by the actor can be positive as indicated by the green line and the red line indicates negative sentiment. This sentiment is obtained from the researcher's perspective on the articles that have been collected. The article is read and marked with any parts that express the actor's opinion. Actors are written in organizational form because they have better credibility than individuals.

After analyzing and mapping the sentiments of each actor, 5 actors were obtained who expressed their opinions regarding education-based tourism. The five actors are considered to have the capability to convey their statements. The five actors are:

1. NGO (Non-Governmental Organization)
2. Academics
3. Government
4. Public
5. Private Sector

Table 1. Course Network Analysis Mapping Analysis

No.	Actor	Problem	Key Issues	Sentiment
1.	NGOs	Environmentally based tourism development must be developed. Educational tourism must be developed especially to introduce nature to visitors.	Nature Education	Positive
		Pure nature based tourism displaced due to development. Artificial tourism development often ignores the sustainability of the surrounding environment, so this is a common problem that must be immediately anticipated. Tourism has the aim of earning income.	Nature Education	Positive
2.	Academics	Educational tourism is a learning innovation. Basically, educational tourism is an innovation to provide a place to play and learn. Learning will be fun if done together in the concept of play.	Innovation	Positive
		Focus on nature tourism development. Educational tourism, especially in Indonesia, would be better if it was directed at environmentally based concepts. Introduction to the environment must be carried out from an early age to students, so that they will be more aware of how important it is to manage the environment for long-term sustainability, especially since the issue of environmental damage is increasingly common everywhere.	Nature Education	Positive
		Research based tourism begins to develop. Research-based educational tourism must be developed to provide benefits to the wider community. The public must be given space to experiment based on research, thereby providing academic experience and opening minds to the importance of learning concepts based on research and to prove a theory or concept that has been developed previously.	Infrastructure	Positive
		Indonesia has natural tourism potential. Indonesia, with its good natural potential, must be protected and cared for, especially as it can be used as a large laboratory for developing educational tourism so that future generations can protect and appreciate nature, and not	Nature Education	Positive

		destroy nature for economic purposes.		
		Learning isn't just in the classroom. Learning does not have to be done in a formal classroom or school, but can also be done informally, namely through educational tours to provide learning to students.	Education Tourism Development	Positive
		Educational tourism is a global development. Educational tourism was developed to keep up with global developments which are increasingly massive and demand updates to tourism concepts and provide a broad view to the public that tourism has a good impact on developing oneself.	Education Tourism Development	Positive
		Educational tourism must be informative and creative. Educational tourism must provide information that is useful to the public, so that it has positive value for the development of science. Then educational tourism must be managed creatively so that visitors do not get bored and are interested in visiting again.	Innovation	Positive
3.	Government	Technology based tourism development. Currently, technological developments are being carried out intensively, so it is an opportunity to develop education-based tourism in the field of technology as an effort to provide experience and learning to students.	Technology	Positive
		Tourism must be preserved. Educational tourism needs to be preserved and developed comprehensively to provide learning for the public	Education	Positive
		Historical tourism must be developed for education. Historically based educational tourism has excellent learning value for students' learning, but its development is less intensive and maintenance is poor. Historically based tourism should be maintained and cared for because it can be used as a laboratory for historical learning and introduce the importance of preserving historical remains to future generations.	Historical	Positive
		Educational tourism is industrial revolution. Tourism will continue to develop according to global needs. In the future, education-based tourism	Education Tourism Development	Positive

		will also experience a transformation in the concept of learning.		
4.	Public	Educational tourism does not yet have optimal capacity. Indonesia does not yet have adequate educational tourism provisions, so it must continue to be developed to provide science-based tourism facilities.	Infrastructure	Negative
		The importance of ecocratic tourism. Currently, ecocracy tourism is developing, namely tourism management based on the eco green concept, so that managers must pay attention to this to protect the environment around tourist attractions.	Human Resources	Positive
		Communities need public spaces for educational tourism. Public space is a right and obligation that the government must fulfill to the people, to provide space for creativity and tourism.	Education Tourism Development	Positive
		Many public spaces were displaced. Many public spaces in Indonesia are not managed well. In fact, public space must be provided to the community and can be used as intended. Public space governance must be evaluated and conceptualized well and precisely, so that it realizes the right public space goals for society.	Education Tourism Development	Negative
		Tourism facilities and management are not good. One of the obstacles to managing education-based tourism in Indonesia is poor facilities and management, which becomes an obstacle to long-term sustainability.	Education Tourism Development	Negative
		Public space is a form of humanist concern. Public spaces, especially in urban areas, are a means for people to enjoy the green and beautiful atmosphere of the city, so this must be considered in every policy formulation by the government.	Facilities	Positive
		5.	Private Sector	Educational tourism must be accessible to everyone. Education-based tourism must be enjoyed by every level of society, not just certain people.
Educational tourism must collaborate with schools. The aim of developing the concept of educational tourism is to provide learning outside of school	Education Tourism Development			Positive

		as an effort to balance students' learning needs. Tourist attraction providers must work together to provide this space.		
		Synergy and collaboration program. There needs to be synergy and collaboration between stakeholders in the pentahelix concept to develop educational tourism.	Stakeholders	Positive
		Integrated educational tourism for students. Educational tourism must provide space for student collaboration in learning methods.	Stakeholders	Positive

Based on the results of DNA analysis in the form of images and tables above, an overview can be obtained that discusses the development of education-based tourism in Indonesia. The analysis results show that there are 5 actors, and each actor conveys their own sentiments. The first actor photographed was an NGO (Non Governmental Organization). The NGO expressed 2 opinions and overall they were positive. The first opinion states that the importance of nature-based educational tourism needs to be developed for the wider community, with the key issue of this opinion being nature education and its positive nature which influences the development of educational tourism. The second opinion is that tourism development often ignores environmental sustainability, so this is a problem that must be addressed. The key issue of this opinion is nature education, and it has a positive sentiment because it has a good impact on the overall development of educational tourism in Indonesia.

The second actor portrayed in this research is academics, or people who have the capacity to express their opinions regarding the development of educational tourism. The first opinion is that educational tourism is an innovation to provide a place to play and learn. The key issue of this opinion is innovation and has a positive sentiment because educational tourism must be able to provide a place to play and learn. The second opinion is that educational tourism must be environmentally based and managed by human resources. This opinion is included in the key issue human resources category, and has positive sentiment value because environmentally based educational tourism will have an impact on introducing students to the importance of the environment. The third opinion is that research-based educational tourism is important to develop. This opinion is included in the key issue of education tourism development, and has positive sentiment because currently research-based tourism in Indonesia is still minimal and needs to continue to be developed. The fourth opinion is that the vast natural potential in Indonesia must be protected and developed. This opinion is included in the key issue category of nature education, and has a positive sentiment because currently nature damage is a problem in Indonesia, so to maintain better nature, awareness must be given to the public. The fifth opinion is that learning does not have to be done in a classroom or formal school, but can be done in an informal school or educational tour. This opinion is included in the key issue of education tourism development, and has a positive sentiment because with educational tourism students will not get bored if they only study in class. The sixth opinion is that educational tourism was developed to keep up with global developments.

This opinion is included in the key issue of education tourism development, and has a positive sentiment because students are invited to think openly to face global developments. The final or final opinion is that educational tourism must provide benefits to the public. This opinion is

included in the key issue of innovation and has positive sentiment because this is the main goal in developing educational tourism.

The third actor photographed is government, both central and regional, and the overall sentiment expressed is positive. The first opinion expressed was the need for technology-based educational tourism. This opinion is included in the technology key issue category, and has a positive value because technology can be introduced to students from an early age. The second opinion is that educational tourism needs to be preserved and developed. This opinion has the key issue of education tourism development , and has a positive sentiment. The third opinion is that historical-based educational tourism has good learning value for students. This opinion is included in the historical key issue and has a positive sentiment because history learning needs to be introduced to students in order to understand the civilization of the developing era. The fourth opinion is that educational tourism is an industrial revolution. This opinion is included in the key issue of education tourism development , and has positive sentiment.

The fourth actor portrayed in this research is the public with 6 opinions, with 3 sentiments being positive and 3 being negative. The first opinion is that Indonesia does not yet have adequate educational tourism provisions. This opinion falls into the key issue infrastructure category, and has a negative sentiment because the lack of educational tourism will affect students' or the public's interest in visiting. The second opinion is that the development of the current economy has developed and the human resources involved must have capacity. Ecocracy is environmentally based tourism which must be developed and conceptualized appropriately. The key issue of this opinion is human resources and has a positive sentiment because ecocracy can influence awareness of educational tourism governance. The third opinion is that public space is a right and obligation that must be fulfilled by the government. The key issue of this opinion is education tourism development and it is positive because this is needed as a forum for creativity for the public. The fourth opinion is that many public spaces in Indonesia are not managed well. This opinion is included in the key issue of education tourism development , and has a negative sentiment because basically every party, especially the government, manages public spaces for the common good. The fifth opinion is that one of the obstacles to managing educational tourism is poor facilities and management. This opinion is included in the key issue facility, and has negative sentiment. The sixth opinion is that public spaces in urban areas are a means for the community. This opinion is included in the key issue of nature tourism, and has positive sentiment.

The fifth actor is the private sector with 4 opinions, all of which are positive. The first opinion is that education-based tourism must be enjoyed by the whole community. This opinion has the key issue of education. The second opinion is that the purpose of educational tourism is to provide lessons outside of school, and this opinion is included in the key issue of education. The third opinion is that there needs to be synergy and collaboration to develop educational tourism. This opinion is included in the key stakeholder issue. The final or fourth opinion is that educational tourism must collaborate with students, and the key issue of this opinion is stakeholders.

From the results of the overall DNA analysis above, factors were found that influence educational tourism in Indonesia in general based on the word key issues, namely:

1. Nature education
2. Innovation
3. Educational tourism development

4. Infrastructure
5. Human Resources
6. Facilities
7. Technology
8. Historical
9. Stakeholders

The development of educational tourism as an educational development sector in Indonesia is a strategic step to increase the attraction for the public, especially school students, to provide learning outside the classroom and increase their knowledge. Based on the results of DNA analysis, the following is a recommended model that can be adopted by stakeholders in improving and developing educational tourism in Indonesia.

Figure 2. Recommendation Model for Educational Tourism Development

Based on the model above, to develop educational tourism you must pay attention to various aspects that are collaborated with the concept of dynamic governance thinking, which in this model is as a moderator. The main things that must be considered are technology, natural education, historical education, and human resources. These main factors can be used as a basis for innovation that is collaborated with stakeholders. Innovation and stakeholders must undergo further review based on the concept of dynamic governance which has 3 thinking concepts, namely thinking ahead which is defined as the ability to identify environmental factors that influence the implementation of future development, understand the impact on the socio-economic society, identify possible investment options. society takes advantage of new opportunities and avoids potential threats that could hinder society's progress. This is very important to apply in the development of educational tourism in Indonesia, which must consider sustainability in the short, medium and long term. The dynamics of problems that arise must be anticipated through alternative policy options that are adapted to the conditions of each region.

Then thinking again which has the definition of reviewing various policies, strategies and programs currently underway, including in planning the development of educational tourism in

general. Have the results achieved by policies, strategies and programs met the expectations of many parties or do they need to be redesigned to get better quality results? The time frame for conducting a review starts from the conditions currently faced until the period when policies, strategies and programs are in effect, by comparing what has been achieved with what is desired. And the last one is thinking across which is the ability to adopt thoughts, opinions and other ideas outside the framework of thinking (mindset) that has traditionally been attached to and become the basis for doing something. By learning from the experiences and thoughts of other people in managing a country or government, you will get fresh ideas and thoughts in carrying out innovations to improve policies, strategies and programs to improve people's welfare. This can be attributed to the adoption of concepts that have developed in other regions or countries. Indonesia, as a country that has such good potential and a future demographic bonus that will be an advantage, must be utilized well to form competent human resources through formal and informal learning, so to develop the concept of educational tourism we can adopt those that have developed abroad. All of these variables/factors will influence the final goal, namely the development of education-based tourism in Indonesia.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and presentation in the previous section, it can be concluded that tourism is one of the highest foreign exchange contributors in Indonesia. Tourism has various types, one of which is educational tourism. The development of educational tourism has interesting dynamics that need to be reviewed further, especially the problems that arise and how dynamic policies can overcome them. Based on the results of the analysis, 5 actors were successfully captured in this research, namely non-governmental organizations, academics, government, public and private sectors. The actor expressed his opinions in articles or mass media regarding the development of educational tourism in Indonesia. Based on further analysis, several key issues or variables were obtained that influence the development of educational tourism in Indonesia, namely nature education, innovation, infrastructure, human resources, facilities, technology, history and stakeholders. All of these variables have the ultimate aim of educational tourism development which is moderated by the concept of dynamic governance, namely thinking ahead, thinking again, and thinking across.

REFERENCES

- Neo, B. S., & Chen, G. (2007). *Dynamic governance: Embedding culture, capabilities and change in Singapore (English version)*. WorldScientific.
- Nugroho, SBM. (2020). Several Problems in the Development of the Tourism Sector in Indonesia. Semarang: Diponegoro University.
- Leifeld, P., & Haunss, S. (2011). Political discourse networks and the conflict over software patents in Europe. *European Journal of Political Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-6765.2011.02003.x>
- Roger, D. (1998). Leisure, Learning and Travel. *Journal of Physical Education, Research and Dance*, 69(4), pp.28-31.
- Smith, M., & Kelly, C. (2006). Holistic Tourism: Journeys of the Self? *Tourism Recreation Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508281>